

STRATEGIES FOR ENSURING ENERGY SYSTEM RESILIENCE IN THE CONTEXT OF RENEWABLE ENERGY INTEGRATION

Abstract. The integration of renewable energy sources (RES) into power systems offers significant benefits for sustainability but also introduces challenges related to variability, uncertainty, and the resilience of the energy infrastructure. This study explores advanced strategies and technologies to enhance the resilience of energy systems, emphasizing mobile energy storage systems (MESS), distributed energy resources (DER), and artificial intelligence (AI)-driven monitoring and adaptation solutions. The findings highlight the interconnected roles of economic, environmental, and technological factors in achieving resilient energy systems.

Introduction. The global shift towards renewable energy sources (RES) is essential for mitigating climate change and achieving sustainability goals. However, the integration of RES poses challenges to the resilience of power systems due to their inherent variability and susceptibility to extreme events. Resilient energy systems are crucial to ensure stable operations, minimize disruptions, and adapt to adverse conditions. This paper examines advanced resilience strategies, focusing on mobile energy storage systems (MESS), distributed energy resources (DER), and AI-enabled solutions as pivotal tools in addressing these challenges.

Methods. This study employs a systematic review and analysis of existing resilience strategies in energy systems, with data synthesized from recent publications and case studies. Key methodologies include:

1. Evaluation of resilience metrics for energy systems, incorporating probabilistic models and real-time optimization [1].
2. Analysis of mobile and distributed energy solutions using Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) for cost and resilience trade-offs [2].
3. Review of AI-driven anomaly detection frameworks for monitoring and adapting to disruptions in energy networks [3].

Results and Discussion

Mobile Energy Storage Systems (MESS) and Distributed Energy Resources (DER). MESS and DER play a critical role in mitigating the impact of disruptions. Studies show that pre-positioning MESS in strategic locations significantly reduces expected load curtailment during extreme events [4]. Integration with DER enhances operational flexibility, enabling local energy supply during outages and minimizing dependence on centralized infrastructure [5].

Artificial Intelligence in Resilience Enhancement. AI-driven anomaly detection and prediction systems improve real-time monitoring and decision-making, allowing systems to address potential disruptions preemptively. Machine

learning models, such as LSTM and reinforcement learning algorithms, effectively optimize resource allocation under uncertainty [6].

Economic and Environmental Implications. The adoption of resilience strategies, such as DER and MESS, reduces recovery times and operational costs while supporting decarbonization goals. Optimization models indicate that these technologies contribute to both economic resilience and environmental sustainability by reducing dependency on fossil fuels [7].

Conclusion. Enhancing the resilience of energy systems in the context of renewable energy integration requires a multifaceted approach. Mobile and distributed energy solutions and AI-driven technologies are pivotal in building adaptive, cost-effective, and sustainable energy infrastructures. Policymakers and industry stakeholders should prioritize these strategies to ensure robust energy systems capable of withstanding future challenges.

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